

Adoption of Alternative Learning System (ALS) Teachers in Learning Management System (LMS) in Cavite Province, Philippines: A Hierarchical Regression Analysis

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to determine the awareness of Alternative Learning System (ALS) teachers on existing open source learning management systems (LMS) and the extent of their utilization. An adopted instrument was utilized and administered to ALS teachers (N = 89) from sixteen (16) municipalities and two (2) cities in Cavite Province. A hierarchical regression analysis was conducted to determine the influence of ALS teacher-related factors (age, gender, availability and skills on computer and internet, and awareness and use of LMS). It was revealed that 87 (97.75%) of the respondents were aware on the availability and usability of LMS. Moreover, ALS teachers were either occasionally or seldom consider the use of LMS in their learning season activities as a tool in learning session. Three steps in hierarchical regression analysis were conducted on the use of learning management systems on the factors (age; gender; availability and skills on computer and internet; and awareness on LMS) towards the adoption of LMS. It was disclosed that 8 percent of ALS teachers use of LMS is accounted for the age and gender (Adjusted R² = 0.008). When technical availability (computer and Internet access) and technical capability (computer skills and Internet skills) are added to the second step of the analysis, their combined predictive power is 65 percent (Adjusted R² = 0.065). Technical availability and technical capability were able to increase the predictive power of the regression model by 14.9 percent (Δ Adjusted R² = 0.149). Age, internet access and internet skills in this step displayed a significant influence on the ALS teacher's adoption of LMSs. Overall, the internet skills (β = 0.323) was the strongest predictor of ALS teachers related factors and use of LMSs followed by computer skills (β = 0.283) and awareness (β = 0.190), internet access (β = 0.179), gender (β = 0.138), computer access (β = -0.148), and age (β = -0.335) respectively. This result implies that 97.75% of ALS teacher give a little consideration to the issue or not at all in open source LMSs as a tool for ALS out-of-school youth and adult learning session.

Keywords: Alternative Learning System, Awareness, Learning Management System, Hierarchical Regression

INTRODUCTION

The Alternative Learning System through the Department of Education provides Quality, equitable and accessible education to every Filipino Out-of-School Youth and Adult, a second chance education program. In general, the implementation of ALS plays a progressive and remarkable success in the Department of Education, Philippines since it launched and its historical enrollment from 2016-2019 an increasing trend from 537,666 to 739,872 learners (The World Bank, 2016). However, for School Year 2020-2021 the enrollment data down to 384,027 last September 21, 2020 due to COVID-19 pandemic (UP School of Economics, 2020).

Moreover, Alternative Learning System (ALS) implementers, facilitators and teachers should adopt and develop better strategies on handling ALS learning session during and after the COVID-19 pandemic with the emphasis on distance and blended learning modality. In this modality technology affecting how implementers, facilitators and teachers teach in basic education specifically for Alternative Learning System. In the Department of Education System, the tools which are mostly used include books, teachers, infrastructure and partially open- source software (OSS) (Verts, T. 2008; Rothwell, R., 2008). E-learning has become one of the fastest-moving trends in education and poses a promising alternative to traditional learning (Zhang et.al 2004). The rapid development of information technologies provides tools to expand and support e-learning applications in the basic education system. One of the major technological innovations to support e-learning system is Learning Management System (LMS). The private basic education sector specifically in the new normal set up in education implement LMS to support their basic education curriculum with many types of tools; such as discussion boards, forum, chat, online grade posting, online exam, file sharing, management of assignment, lesson planning, class schedule and announcements.

Furthermore, in public educations through the office of the Undersecretary of Administration release the AIDE MEMOURE dated July 01, 2020 the release of Learning Management System (LMS) and Electronic Self-Learning Modules (E-SLMS) that can be used by teachers and learners who would like to adopt online classes as the modality by which learning would be delivered (DepEd Commons, 2020). Proper implementation of these tools is important for the success of basic education system, however, most of the time; implementation of such systems may be problematic and even may end with a failure (Legris et.al, 2003). Successful implementation of this technology partly depends on factors related to attitude and opinions of teachers, learners, information technologies and department/division support. Although stakeholders are primary considerations of LMS for successful implementation, teachers play a central role in the effectiveness and success of

e-learning based subject (Davis et.al,1989; Webster and Hackley,1997; Selim, 2007). Change is an important theme associated with technology, but some teachers wonder whether they should embrace it into their classroom practices (Dunn et.al, 2011). The personal willingness of teachers to adopt and integrate innovations into their classroom practices is the key for successful innovation (Gess et.al, 2003; Ghaith, 1997; Groff, 2008). Considering the predicaments and collected facts from these studies, the authors decided to conduct a study. This study attempts to determine the awareness and adoption of ALS teachers of Learning Management System.

This study attempts to determine the awareness of the faculty in terms of knowledge in LMS's. Towards this goal, it will answer the following questions:

1. What are the ALS Teacher-related factors in terms of age, gender, computer access at home, Internet access at home, and awareness on learning management system?
2. What is the awareness of ALS teacher in terms of knowledge on learning management system?
3. To what extent did they use the learning management system?
4. Do teacher-related factors and awareness on the learning management system influence the use of learning management system?

Learning Management Systems

LMS is software used for delivering, tracking and managing training/education. LMSs range from systems for managing training/educational records to software for distributing courses over the Internet and offering features for online collaboration (Kotzer & Elran, 2011). Most LMS share the following generic features such as automatic enrollment and reminders for mandatory subjects, options for manager access, such as to approve materials or participation, integration with human resource systems for tracking employment eligibility, performance goals, and similar corporate priorities, control over access and class groupings according to a number of metrics, such as geography, involvement in a particular project, or levels of security clearance (Ellis, 2009) in this study, several examples of LMSs such as MOODLE and Edmodo were asked to faculty members to measure their level of awareness and utilization.

Technology Adoption

For school to successfully integrate any new tool or system, organizational structures and adequate technological affordances are important (Saunders, 2012). In addition, researchers noted, if however, teachers are not involved in the process, and their concerns are not addressed, the adoption of any innovation will remain largely unsuccessful (Lochner et al., 2015). In the study of Bringula (2013) concluded

that commitment was a strong positive force that could push older people to use internet technologies and technical and non-technical aspects influence web portal usability. Lastly, according to Aldunate and Nussbaun, (2013) five technology factors influence the likelihood of adoption: relative advantage, compatibility, complexity, trialability and observability.

Technology Awareness

In the study of Juhary (2013) mention after three years of purchase, the LMS at the defense university called 'My Online Classroom e-Learning' has not been the effective teaching and learning tool as expected. By this, in his paper argues on two levels. First, the poor usage of the LMS by the academics and second, the questionable quality of the contents put on the LMS. Moreover, the awareness of LMS application mention of Embi and Adun (2010) concurred with the importance of published policies and they found that only eight public Universities in Malaysia have a recognized policy on e-learning and their LMS, it is not surprising then that academics do not pay close attention to the importance of using the LMS. It is argued that it is not the matter of under-utilization of the LMS that is so disquieting, but the fact that students need to have viable learning options and academics should be using the 'right tool for the right job' (Beatty & Ulasewicz, 2007). Furthermore Bates and Sangra (2011) claimed that LMS are the main driver of e-learning in tertiary education. This is because about 90% tertiary providers in the United States have LMS (Lokken and Womer, 2007). In addition, Metaxiotis and Psarras (2003) found out that knowledge management can be better applied in the higher education institution by creating a flexible and innovative relationship between work and education, helping students to match their talents more closely to their current workplace demands, contributing to the adaptation and assimilation of new knowledge with existing ones as well as contributing to the re-connection of learning with experience.

Hierarchical regression

In the article posted on statistic.com Hierarchical regression, on the other hand, deals with how predictor (independent) variables are selected and entered into the model. They mention, specifically, hierarchical regression refers to the process of adding or removing predictor variables from the regression model in steps, Hierarchical regression also includes forward, backward, and stepwise regression, in which predictors are automatically added or removed from the regression model in steps based on statistical algorithms, these forms of hierarchical regression are useful if you have a very large number of potential predictor variables and want to determine (statistically) which variables have the most predictive power. Some literature notes that, Simple linear regression models have been used—and still are used—to analyze (LSA) or Latent Semantic Analysis data. But these models have weaknesses. One is the underlying assumption that individuals answer independently of the cluster they belong to (Burstein, 1980; Rogosa, 1978). Another

is the assumption that, in terms of magnitude and direction, relationships within each group are the same as those across groups. Ignoring the nested structure of the data can lead to aggregation bias, ecological fallacy (Peterson, 1994; Robinson, 1950), and misestimates of the precision (Aitkin et al., 1981). Apart from these technicalities, most linear models do not allow for analyzing the group effect on the individuals or the different effects of an explanatory variable that is group dependent. It is possible to illustrate this problem within the context of the / introductory example above by investigating how much of the variability of the achievement scores in the full population can be explained by introducing socioeconomic status (SES) as a group-level effect.

METHODOLOGY

The resulting survey instrument used in this descriptive study is adapted from the framework of Garcia et. al, (2021) focusing on the profile, awareness and extent of use of LMS by faculty members. The study was conducted during the Division seminar-workshop on digital citizenship and responsibility and digital game based learning 2022 specifically for ALS teachers and implementers in Cavite Province. Using Slovin's formula, (n) given the population size (N) and a margin of error(e). It is computed as $n = N / (1+Ne^2)$, 116 respondents were randomly selected to answer the survey questionnaire and 89 questionnaires were retrieved. The study used frequency count, percentage and means to describe data. Hierarchical regression analysis was used to determine the influence of faculty-related factors and use of learning management system.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

RQ1.

Table 1. Age

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean
Age	89	30	57	43.03

Table 2. Gender

	F	%
Female	76	85.39
Male	13	14.61

Table 1 and 2 shows the demographic profile of 89 ALS facilitators/implementers and teachers handling ALS learning session as participants of the study. Table 1 show that the average age of respondents was 43.03. It can be gleaned on table 2 that there was 85.39 percent are female and 14.61 percent are male respondents who participated in the survey.

Table 3. Technical Availability

	f	%
With Computer Access at Home	89	100
Without Computer Access at Home	0	0.00
With Internet Access at Home	85	95.5

Table 3 indicates that 100 percent of the respondents have computer access at home (f = 89), this reflects that 100 percent have computer at home. Although there are only 95.5 percent respondents who have Internet access

RQ3.

Table 6. Use of open source LMSs

	f	%
Never	85	95.51
Occasionally	4	4.49
Frequently	0	0.00
Always	0	0.00

at home, it can be inferred that most of them still access the Internet after their work.

Table 4. Technical Capability

	Not Skilled %	Beginner %	Intermediate %	Advanced %	Expert %
Computer Usage Skills	0.00	0.00	54	33	0.00
Internet Usage Skills	0.00	0.00	63	22	2

In table 4 specifies how the respondent personally evaluates themselves in terms of computer and internet capability, along with the common equivalent of numbers beginner and expert column receives the same value. Most of the respondents fall between intermediate and advance users.

RQ2.

Table 5. Awareness on LMS

	F	%
Not aware	2	2.25
Aware	87	97.75

Table 5 states that respondents were mostly aware on the availability and usability of Learning Management Systems. This is observed by the percentage of aware a ALS teachers respondent which is 97.75% compared to the 2.25% unaware respondents, the difference is high, and this likely suggests the impact in the utilization of Learning Management Systems in basic education learning session activities. The low variance of percentage between aware and unaware respondents which emerges from the observations and data collection reflects the issue of awareness amongst ALS teachers must be properly addressed. In basic education organizations, although it is not part of this study, the absence of e-learning policy together with the Information Communication Technology policy has been the main key that hinders a widespread acceptance of e- learning practices and ultimately the LMS usage. Without a top down instruction on utilizing

the LMS, academics are oblivious to the use of it. It is argued that it is not the matter of under-utilization of the LMS that is so disquieting, but the fact that learners need o have viable learning options and academics should be using the 'right tool for the right job' (Beatty & Ulasewicz, 2007). Students will select learning strategies that best suit them. Whether they are open to the use of the LMS depends on the support from institutions and quality content in the LMS. The application of the LMS will be improved only if the awareness of teachers is comprehensive. Awareness can be generated in the forms of seminars, training and announcements. What is needed is the full force and commitment by different basic education institutions to ensure successful adoption of LMSs that is effective and efficient.

Table 6 suggests that respondents were either occasionally or do not consider the use of LMSs in their learning session activities as a tool and platform in teaching. This can be seen by the high percentages of respondents who never use LMSs (95.51%), and occasionally LMS users (4.49%) and respondents who are inclined in using LMSs in their profession (0%) shows low consideration in using the available and powerful features of LMSs. Nonetheless, it is perplexing that respondents were not partial or rarely uses LMS to teach, the high percentages likely suggest that respondents' options were focused on other traditional teaching platform. Perhaps, the respondents preferred to use other systems for academic activities such as the traditional way of teaching using the blackboard (not reflected in this study) and paper and pencil activities. The results are quite alarming specially that Learning Management Systems are adopted mostly by different foreign institutions and this suggest unavailability of modern learning platforms for students in government basic academic institutions. It's a dependable fact that LMSs usage has changed the learning environment drastically as e-Learning and versatile advances have gone from early-adopter oddities to standard fundamentals. All things considered, the surveyed institutions suggest that there are a lot of conventional organizations out there who aren't into the direction of the greater part of the LMSs build up or can't persuade their academic workers to explore the new trend of eLearning and LMSs.

Table 7 shows the results of three steps hierarchical regression analysis on the use of learning management systems of faculty members on the factors (age; gender; availability and skills on computer and internet; and awareness on LMS) towards the adoption of LMS. It was disclosed that 0.008 percent of the variation in the ALS teachers use of LMS is accounted for the age and gender and gender (Adjusted R² = 0.008). When technical availability (computer and Internet access) and technical capability (computer skills and Internet skills) are added to the second step of the analysis, their combined predictive power is 0.065 percent (Adjusted R² = 0.065). Technical availability and technical capability were able to increase the predictive power of the regression model by 0.119 percent (Δ Adjusted R² =

0.119). In this step, only computer skills and internet skills displayed a significant influence on the ALS teachers LMS adoption. This may be attributed to the presence of computer with internet access the ALS teachers are able to use outside their workplace which allows them to access the LMS at any given time.

Furthermore, the negative beta of age as a predictor of the adoption of an LMS indicates that the older a teachers becomes, the lower his chance to use an LMS. When awareness on LMS is added to the third step of the analysis, their combined predictive power is 14.9 percent (Adjusted R² = 0.149). In this stage, age and internet skills have a significant influence on the ALS teacher's use of LMS ($p \leq 0.05$). However in this model, Internet access no longer predicts the ALS teacher's use of LMS. It can be assumed that teachers become aware as well as convinced to use an LMS if there are peers or co-workers who actually implement it in their respective learning session. Accounting all beta coefficients, the internet skills ($\beta = 0.323$) was the strongest predictor of faculty related factors and use of LMSs followed by computer skills ($\beta = 0.283$) and awareness ($\beta = 0.190$), internet access ($\beta = 0.179$), gender ($\beta = 0.138$), computer access ($\beta = -0.148$), and age ($\beta = -0.335$) respectively.

Table 7. Hierarchical Regression Analysis of ALS Teacher Related Factors and Use of open source LMSs

Predictors	Beta	P-value
<i>Step 1 (Adjusted R² = 0.008; Δ Adjusted R² = 0.002; F=0.784; Significance = 0.000)</i>		
Age	0.036	0.001
Gender	0.243	0.002
<i>Step 2 (Adjusted R² = 0.065; Δ Adjusted R² = 0.119; F=2.844; Significance = 0.000)</i>		
Age	-0.359	0.007
Gender	0.155	0.059
Computer Access	-0.158	0.386
Internet Access	0.231	0.031
Computer Skills	0.564	0.032
Internet Skills	0.612	0.014
<i>Step 3 (Adjusted R² = 0.149; Δ Adjusted R² = 0.085; F=2.911; Significance = 0.000)</i>		
Age	-0.335	0.009
Gender	0.138	0.076
Computer Access	-0.148	0.404
Internet Access	0.179	0.128
Computer Skills	0.283	0.351
Internet Skills	0.323	0.033
Awareness	0.190	0.038

CONCLUSION

After analyzing the result of the study, it was observed that ALS teacher's respondents' deal with some issue related to e-learning knowledge and use. Despite of the availability of different LMSs, there are indicative numbers that implies focus on other materials rather than LMS strategic matters which could have helped teacher inside their respective learning session. This is evident to the low percentage of respondents who are knowledgeable of LMSs availability and extreme low percentage of using them in doing their academic chores to the extent that, for example, respondents were likely relying on traditional ways of getting resources on paper printouts (books, newspapers, etc.) and teaching using blackboards and whiteboards. This result somewhat implies that certain basic public education institutions gives little considerations to the issue or not at all. Technical availability (computer use), Internet availability, and technical capability (skill) are major factors in LMSs consideration, use, and knowledge as the system's functional aspects are found in the web and are mostly used through it.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Results indicate how it is important to discuss LMSs for the basic education in public school, as the % of the results of this study, are pointers to the lack of initiatives of ALS teachers to the LMSs actuality and realization.

The study indicates measures should be considered for e-learning systematic verification of actual performance of learning activities of basic education. Several issues must first be addressed, however, in order to provide the ALS teachers an improved environment for quicker adaption and use like the technical structure of the basic education institution especially in computer and internet architecture. Administrations should be concerned with the percentage of answers indicating zero knowledge of LMS in general, and how this frustrates and hinders the productivity of the ALS teacher. Another issue that should be addressed further is technical training as majority of teachers indicated that they are aware of LMSs existence but are not keen in using them, indicative of zero knowledge into the design or features of the system.

This research somewhat implies and brings to light the issues and concerns ALS teacher have toward the use of their LMS. Understanding into the factors that both hinder and enhance the use of the LMS in learning session are highly recommended to the basic education institution as it would shed light to teacher consideration of available LMSs . Further research may also need to focus on policy issues, including technical support, costs, upgrading of technical infrastructure, security, and the maintenance of the technical aspects that could influence the value and use of the LMS in the basic education. Benchmarking with other public and private basic education institutions locally and abroad will be of big help in the mobilization and utilization of LMS.

As the evaluation shows it attest that the effectiveness of LMS quite needs improvement of

integration in terms of teacher skills and computer literacy, as you can see on the table that was pinpoint in results and discussion numerous users are already found at ease in delivering their modules through the use of LMS. The researchers suggest to ALS basic education to enhance and best introduce other possible, other alternative LMS aside from the most commonly used application mentioned in this paper. The teacher educators have to accept the demand of the modern world and modify their old concepts and methods to provide students with the knowledge and skill to function effectively in this knowledge explosion era.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

The researchers informed the respondents of the purpose of the study, that the latter's participation was voluntary and confidentiality of information was ensured. The respondent's anonymity was guaranteed. They may opt to participate or not by answering the survey questionnaire, the data was collected onsite during the training on digital citizenship for ALS teachers. The respondents expressed their thoughts freely and confidently. There was no conflict of interest since the researchers did not handle the respondents. The data collected were respected and kept private and will be disposed when no longer needed.

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